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Evolution of Nutrient Content of Eggplant Leaves (*Solanum Macrocarpon*) "Gboma" Variety during Plant Growth

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Abstract

Gboma eggplant (Solanum macrocarpon) leaves provide nutrients useful for human well-being. However, several factors influence nutrients rate from the harvest to the consumption it is therefore important to determine the nutrients composition along the plant growth. Gboma eggplant was grown in an experimental field and leaves were harvested and analyzed from 6th week after transplanting to 11th week. The results revealed that vitamin C, beta carotene and proteins rates increased from week 6 to week 9 and then decreased to week 11. The values were respectively $(8.19 \pm 1.65 \text{ mg}/100\text{g}$ to $25.73 \pm 1.65 \text{ mg}/100\text{g}$ then $9.36 \pm 1.65 \text{ mg}/100\text{g}$ for vitamin C, $(112.24 \pm 0.92 \mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ to $210.74 \pm 0.88 \mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ then $60.57 \pm 0.26 \mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) for beta-carotene and $(16.34 \pm 0.4 \%$ to $21.92 \pm 0.8 \%$ then $16.95 \pm 0.16\%$) for proteins. However, lipid rates were constant, oscillating between 4 % and 5 %. The total ash content increased with growth from $17.07 \pm 0.04 \%$ (at 6th week) to $21.6 \pm 0.16 \%$ (at the 11th week). Polyphenols rate increased, from $741.67 \pm 6.56 \text{ mg EAG/g}$ (at 6th week) to $1617.5 \pm 7.07 \text{ mg EAG/g}$ (at 10th week) and then decreased to $1328.33 \pm 4.71 \text{ mg EAG/g}$ (at the 11th week). For flavonoids, the same phenomenon was observed. The values at 6th week increased from $6.08 \pm 0.51 \text{ mg eq/g}$ to $18.08 \pm 0.66 \text{ mg eq/g}$ at 10th week and then decreased to $17.92 \pm 0.31 \text{ mg eq/g}$ at 11th week. The best harvest time is 9th week, corresponding to 3 weeks after flowering whether 15 weeks after planting.

Key words: leafy vegetables, *Solanum macrocarpon* leaves, nutrients, plant growth, experimental field.

1. Introduction

Leaf vegetables play an important role in the daily diet of populations because they are rich in micronutrients such as vitamins A, B9, C, minerals, proteins, polyphenols and are inexpensive (Nafir-Zenati *et al.*, 1993; Dougnon *et al.*, 2012). African eggplant (*Solanum macrocarpon*), also called "Gboma", leaves are also very rich in nutrients. It is a plant of the family Solanaceae like tomato, pepper and eggplant. But in Ivory Coast, they are however part of the marginal leafy vegetables because, based on the quantity of leaves on the market, they represent only 6% of the leafy vegetables on the market (Fondio *et al.*, 2013). Gboma eggplant has a wide variety of uses. Fruits are used as a laxative; the heated and chewed leaves treat sore throats. But most of the time, the fruits and leaves are used as separate vegetables or as vegetables used in the preparation of other dishes (AVRDC, 2005). The cultivation of Gboma eggplant is generally done on peri-urban areas in Abidjan, economic capital of Ivory Coast (Kouamé *et al.*, 2013) and it is done all year. Leaves are harvested normally one week after flowering, which generally takes place 6–9 weeks after transplanting from the nursery (AVRDC, 2005). But this crop is frequently attacked by pests and many pathogens (Djidji and Fondio, 2013; Azandeme-Hounmalon *et al.*, 2014). This constraint obliged producers to use organic and/or mineral over-fertilization, excessive or inappropriate pesticides (Assogba-Komlan *et al.*, 2007) and harvest the leaves before maturity. All these factors do not guarantee the nutritional quality of

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these leafy vegetables. It would therefore be important to evaluate the nutritional value of Gboma leaves during the plant growth. Indeed, on eggplant leaves, studies have been carried out on the evolution of nutrients during cooking and storage (Adebooye and Opabode, 2004; Medoua and Oldewage-Theron, 2014). However, little research has been done on the nutrient composition of the leaves during the growth of the plant.

This present study was conducted to evaluate the nutritional value of eggplant leaves during ripening in the aim to determine the best harvest period.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

Experimental design

Source of raw materials and experimental design

An experimental plot of 60 m² was set up in Bingerville for the realization of this study. The nursery was made in March 2017, in rainfed and plant were transplanted 5 weeks after sowing, in April. A pinch of Chlorpyrifos-ethyl was placed under each plant during transplanting on a log at the rate of 1m between the lines and 0.5 m between the plants on the line. Watering was done in morning and in evening for two weeks after transplanting and if necessary, thereafter (Djidji and Fondio, 2013). Harvesting of the leaves started 6 weeks after transplanting and took place over 6 weeks. Plant size, leaf length and width were taken weekly before harvest. The leaves were harvested early in the morning and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Morphological characteristics

For the study of morphological characteristics, the size of the plants was taken from the collar at the top and the length of the leaves was taken from the petiole at the tip. Flowering took place in the 6th week after transplanting. At 10th week, as the fruits appeared, their masses and diameters were also noted.

2.2.2. Sample preparation

According to the maturity stage, samples were group together, eggplant leaves (600 g) were harvested every week (W6, W7, W8, W9, W10 and W11). These samples were stored in coolers and sent to the laboratory. Once at the laboratory, the leaves were detached from the stems, roughly chopped washed and drained. After removing the amount to be used for analysis in the cooler, the rest of the samples were dried in Samsung air conditioner at 16 °C for 7 days. The dry samples were then reduced to powder using a blender (Moulinex, France) and stored in airtight containers for analysis.

2.2.3. Chemical Composition of eggplant leaves

Dry matter and Moisture content

The moisture content was determined by the difference of weight before and after drying the sample (10 g) in an oven (Biobase, China) at 105°C until constant weight at least or 72 h.

Ash content

Ash fraction was determined by the incineration of dried sample (5 g) in a muffle oven (Pyrolabo, France) at 550°C for 12 h. The percentage residue weight was expressed as ash content.

Protein content

The crude protein content ($N \times 6.25$) was estimated by the macro-kjeldahl nitrogen assay method using a digestion apparatus.

Lipid content

The lipids were extracted by the Soxhlet method with hexane for 7 h and then determined gravimetrically (AFNOR, 1986).

Vitamin C content

Vitamin C was determined by the method of Pongracz *et al.* (1971). A quantity of 10 g of fresh leaves was crushed in 40 ml of metaphosphoric-acetic acid at 3 M in a blender (Moulinex, France). The ground material

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obtained was filtered and centrifuged at 4200 revolutions per minute for 10 minutes. 2,6-Dichloro-phenol-indophenol (2,6-DCPIP) at 0.5 g/l was used to titrate 1 ml of the supernatant.

β-carotene content

For beta-carotene assay, the method of *Tee et al. (1996)* was used. A quantity of 10 g of fresh sample was ground in 40 ml of 96% ethanol in a blender (Moulinex, France). The ground material was spilled into a separator funnel and 100ml of hexane were added to it. The supernatant was evaporated for 24 hours. The optical density was read at 450 nm.

Phenolic compounds content

For quantification of total phenolic compounds, samples were ground in a grinder (IKAMAG) and 10 g of each powder were soaked in 100 ml of methanol/water solution (80:20, v/v). The mixture was shaken with an orbital shaker (Biobase) for 24 hours. After that, it was filtered with Whatman paper n°1 and the filtrate was stored in an oven (Biobase) at 40°C during 24 hours for solvent evaporation. The final paste was the total extract. Total phenolic compounds were determined by Folin-Ciocalteu method at 765nm and expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE) in milligrams per gram DM using a standard curve generated with gallic acid.

Flavonoids content:

Total flavonoids were determined at 415nm and expressed as quercetin equivalents (QE) in microgram per gram DM using the standard curve of quercetin (*Bala et al., 2014*).

Total sugars and reducing sugars contents

The determination of total sugars and reducing sugars was done according to the method of *Dubois et al. (1956)* modified by *Agbo et al. (1986)*. The ethano-soluble sugars were first extracted with 96% ethanol. The total sugars were then dosed using 5% phenol and concentrated sulfuric acid. The optical density was determined using a spectrophotometer at 490 nm. While the reducing sugars have been dosed using dinitro salicylic acid (DNS). The optical density was read at 540 nm.

2.2.4. Statistical analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) made using the Duncan's test performed at significance level 0.05 to determine the importance of the difference over the weeks of culture. Statistical analysis was performed using STATISTICA software version 7.1.

Results and discussion

3. Results

3.1. Morphological characteristics

The results in Figure 1 show that plant size increases by about 11 cm per week (35 cm at week 6, 52 cm at week 7, 61.5 cm at week 8, 75 cm at week 9, 88.7 cm at week 10 and 93.9 cm at week 11). There is a significant difference over the weeks. However, the length and width of the leaves remain almost equal over the weeks ($P>0.05$). Approximately 35 cm for leaf length and 22 cm for width. There is a significant difference between these data.

The flowering time of 6 weeks after transplanting was consistent with the 6 to 9 weeks after transplanting reported by AVRDC (2012) for the flowering of Gboma eggplants. The increase in the plant size over the weeks reflects favorable conditions for good plant growth. However, plant size, the length and width of the leaves at 11 weeks after transplanting were greater than those noted by *Fondio et al. (2008)* for *Solanum macrocarpon* 12 weeks after transplanting. These differences can be explained by the nature of the soil, the species of *S. macrocarpon* studied or even the rainfall. Indeed, in rainy season, the conditions being favorable, the plants synthesized more easily the nutritive elements (*Fondio et al., 2013*).

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Figure 1: Morphological characteristics of eggplant plants according to the weeks of cultivation. The means of the histograms topped with different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to the statistical test. **SP:** Size of plants; **LL:** Leaf length; **LW:** Leaf width;

3.2. Chemical Composition of eggplant leaves

Moisture, Vitamin C and β -carotene content

Results show that the level of biochemical parameters (Moisture, Vitamin C and β -carotene content) varies with the increase week (Figure 2).

3.2.1. Humidity rate

The percentage of water in eggplant leaves decreased over the weeks from $85.4 \pm .48\%$ in week 6 to $74.51 \pm 0.44\%$ in week 11 that's a water loss of about 12 % (Figure 2). These results differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$).

During photosynthesis, photoassimilates are produced which increase dry matter content and reduce the need for water (Johane, 2016). This phenomenon could explain the decrease in the moisture content over the weeks. These water contents, which nevertheless remain high (80.74% MF on average), give the leaves a very limited shelf life. The results obtained by Dougnon *et al.* (2012) on the leaves of *Solanum macrocarpon* bought in a garden in Benin (88.6% MF) are like those obtained in our study at the 6th week after transplanting (85.4% MF). This indicated that the younger the leaves, the fresher they are.

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Figure 2: Evolution of humidity percentage of Gboma eggplant leaves according to the weeks of cultivation. The means of the histograms topped with different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to the statistical test. **Fa:** eggplant leaves; W6, W7, W8, W9, W10, W11: 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11th weeks after transplanting.

Vitamin C and β -carotene content

Vitamin C content increases from the 6th (8.19 ± 1.65 mg/100g) to the 9th (25.73 ± 1.65 mg/100g) week when it peaks and then decreases at the 10th and 11th week (10.53 ± 0.01 mg/100g and 9.36 ± 1.65 mg/100g respectively) (Figure 3). Vitamin C levels in weeks 7, 8 and 9 are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Like vitamin C, the beta-carotene content increases from week 6 (112.24 ± 0.92 μ g/100g) to week 9 (210.74 ± 0.88 μ g/100g) and then decreases in weeks 10 and 11 (65.23 ± 0.83 μ g/100g and 60.57 ± 0.26 μ g/100g respectively).

The progressive increase of vitamin C and beta-carotene content up to week 9 and then its decrease in weeks 10 and 11 is due to plant maturity and photooxidation, because they are light sensitive vitamins (Herzog *et al.*, 1993; Tessier, 2012; Johane, 2016). The vitamin C content of eggplant leaves at the 9th week is lower than those obtained by Soro *et al.* (2012) for black nightshade (42.22 mg / 100 g MF), by Yang *et al.* (2006) for moringa leaves (257 mg / 100 g MF) and by Acho *et al.* (2014) for *S. melongena* leaves (40 mg/100g). However, it is higher than the results obtained by Antia *et al.* (2006) for potato leaf (15.2 mg/100 g MF). The beta-carotene levels obtained in this study are lower than those of moringa leaves obtained by Martin Price (2007) (6800 μ g/100 g). In the study by Agbo and collaborators (2012), the amount of beta-carotene in roselle at the 5th week of cultivation (64.12 mg /100g) and in mallow jute at the 6th week of cultivation (40.08 mg /100g) is also higher than those obtained in our study. The consumption of eggplant leaves alone in our study does not cover the nutritional requirements which are between 450 and 750 μ g (ANSE, 2019). It would be advisable to consume them with another source of beta-carotene as an adequate intake of beta-carotene is essential for normal growth and development, good vision and eye health, a strong immune system and healthy skin.

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Figure 3: Evolution of the vitamin C content of Gboma eggplant leaves according to the weeks of cultivation

The means of the histograms topped with different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to the statistical test. **Fa** : eggplant leaves

Figure 4: Evolution of the beta-carotene content of Gboma eggplant leaves according to the weeks of cultivation

The means of the histograms topped with different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to the statistical test. **Fa** : eggplant leaves;

Total and reducing sugar rates

The percentage of total sugars and reducing sugars increases over the weeks (from 5.93 ± 0.18 to $8.53 \pm 0.57\%$ for total sugars and from 0.26 ± 0.04 to $0.44 \pm 0.02\%$ for reducing sugars from week 6 to week 11) (Table 1).

Like all organisms, plants require energy for growth. This energy is supplied to him through photosynthesis. It is used for its growth or stored in its reserve organs (fruits for example) (Eveland and

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Jackson, 2012). The increase of sugars in the leaves is therefore due to photosynthesis and the presence in the fruits during storage (Kirigia *et al.*, 2018). Admittedly, the amount of total sugars in this study is higher than those obtained by Yang *et al.* (2006) for moringa leaves (2.93%) and that obtained by Kane *et al.* (2010) on *Lippia multiflora* leaves (0.09%). However, the leaves of Gboma eggplant still have a low content of free sugars. They can therefore be consumed at will without risk of hyperglycaemia by diabetics.

Lipid rate

Lipid content does not vary significantly ($P>0.05$). These levels ranged from 4 to 5% from week 6 to week 11. However, it varies significantly ($P>0.05$) (Table 1).

Leafy vegetables contain very little lipids. Our results are consistent with those obtained by Adjatin *et al.* (2006) on *Amaranthus hybridus* and *Celosia argentea* leaves which have a low content of 4.0% and 5.8% lipids respectively. They also conform to those of Agbaire and Emoyan (2012) for the leaves of *Myrianthus arboreus* with 4.8% lipids. However, the vegetable diet based on leafy vegetables provides the body with the necessary amount of lipids, especially since lipids play an essential role in the constitution of cell membranes.

Protein rate

Protein percentage increases from 16.34 ± 0.4 at week 6 to 21.92 ± 0.8 at week 9 and then decreases to 16.95 ± 0.16 at 11 weeks (Table 1). This variation may be due to fruit development and plant age because during the reproduction period, the nutrients synthesized go first to the fruit (Johane, 2016). In addition, protein synthesis is more active in young plants because they need amino acids to grow well (Agbo *et al.*, 2012). The protein content of the eggplant leaves in our study is lower than that of the leaves of *Amaranthus hybridus* L, *Manihot esculentus* Crantz. and *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. which contain 28.3%, 36.8% and 30.6% protein respectively, but higher than that of *Gynandropsis gynandra* L. which has 16.6% (Adjatin, 2006). It is also higher than the leaf content of *Myrianthus arboreus* and moringa (6.16 and 6.7% protein respectively) (Martin Price, 2007; Agbaire and Emoyan, 2012).

Total ash content

The total ash content increases over the weeks. It varies significantly from $17.07\pm 0.04\%$ at week 6 and $21.6\pm 0.16\%$ at week 11 ($P\leq 0.05$).

This could be due to the richness of the soil in mineral elements and the rainy season, as plants synthesize nutrients more easily during this season (Fondio *et al.*, 2013). These increasing levels could also be due to the appearance of fruits even though their ash content is lower than that of leaves in the 6th week ($10.75\pm 0.29\%$ and $11.3\pm 0.16\%$ in the 10th and 11th week respectively). These values observed for the leaves of Gboma eggplant are higher than those reported by Antia *et al.* (2006) who found 11.1% ash for potato leaves; they are still higher than those of adult leaves of which is 12% (Kane *et al.*, 2010) but lower than those of spinach which is 30.62% (Itoua *et al.*, 2015). A high level of total ash reflects the amount of minerals preserved in a food. This high ash content thus shows that Gboma eggplant leaves could be a potential food source of minerals.

Polyphenol contents

Total polyphenol and flavonoid levels vary considerably ($P\leq 0.05$) over the weeks. They increase from week 6 to week 10 and then decrease slightly by week 11. These are 741.67 ± 6.56 mg EAG/g at week 6, 1612.5 ± 7.07 mg EAG/g at week 10 and 1328.33 ± 4.71 mg EAG/g at week 11 for total polyphenols and 6.08 ± 0.51 mg eq/g at week 6, 18.08 ± 0.66 mg eq/g at week 10 and 17.92 ± 0.31 mg eq/g at week 11 for flavonoids.

These variations in total polyphenol and flavonoid levels could be due to the age of the plants, as the

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younger they are, the greater their capacity to synthesize the nutrients required for their growth (Bellecir, 2008; Agbo *et al.*, 2012, Causse *et al.*, 2013). Compared to the total polyphenol content obtained for moringa (680 mg EAG/g) (Yang *et al.*, 2006), the eggplant leaves in our study contained higher levels even at the 6th week. The high flavonoid content observed in these studied leaves could confer them these anti-viral, anti-tumors, anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic properties that are beneficial to the health of the consumer (Auquire, 2002).

Table I: Nutritional value of « Gboma » eggplant leaves

	FA W6	FA W7	FA W8	FA W9	FA W10	FA W11
% Total Sugars	5,93±0,18 ^a	5,88±0,41 ^a	5,92±0,17 ^a	7,69±0,31 ^b	8,57±0,4 ^c	8,53±0,57 ^c
%Reducing Sugars	0,26±0,04 ^a	0,27±0,02 ^a	0,24±0,01 ^a	0,25±0,05 ^a	0,28±0,04 ^a	0,44±0,02 ^b
% Lipids	4,47±0,16 ^a	4,42±0,05 ^a	4,37±0,04 ^a	4,66±0,33 ^{ab}	5,02±0,24 ^b	5,01±0,05 ^b
% Proteins	16,34±0,4 ^a	18,33±0,3 ^c	21,71±0,31 ^d	21,92±0,8 ^d	17,28±0,06 ^b	16,95±0,16 ^{ab}
% Total ash	17,05±0,04 ^a	17,7±0,08 ^b	18,05±0,04 ^c	18,35±0,04 ^d	20,35±0,2 ^e	21,6±0,16 ^f
Polyphnols (mg EAG/g)	741,67±6,56 ^a	757,5±5,4 ^b	862,5±8,9 ^c	912,5±5,4 ^d	1612,5±7,07 ^f	1328,33±4,71 ^e
Flavonoids (mg eq/g)	6,08±0,51 ^a	10,83±0,66 ^b	11,58±0,62 ^c	11,83±0,31 ^d	18,08±0,66 ^f	17,92±0,31 ^e

The means of the same line bearing different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to the statistical test.

Conclusion

The aim of this study in experimental field was to follow the evolution of nutrients in eggplant (*Solanum macrocarpon*) leaves. Gboma" eggplant leaves are rich in nutrients, such as beta-carotene, polyphenols, flavonoides, proteins. This plant could therefore be an important food resource for the Ivorian populations. According to the results obtained, while the size of the eggplant plants increases per week, the length and width of the leaves remain almost equal. As for the nutrients analyzed, the quantity of vitamin C, beta-carotene, proteins, total polyphenols and flavonoids increases from week 6 to week 9 (10 for polyphenols and flavonoids) where it reaches its peak and then decreases. In addition, the content of dry matter, total sugars and reducing increases over the weeks.

The results showed that the best harvest time or the period when the nutrients are in greatest quantity, is the 3rd week after flowering corresponding to the 9th week after transplanting in the case of our study. It would therefore be desirable to harvest Gboma eggplant leaves at this period. As the leaves are eaten in cooked form and then subjected to nutrients losses during cooking, it will be great to applied cooking preservation methods to optimize nutrients rate in the leaves.

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